

THE USE OF NITROSO DERIVATIVES AS REAGENTS IN INORGANIC ANALYSIS. PART I.

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α -Nitroso- β -naphthylamine, β -nitroso- α -naphthylamine and isonitrosodimedone are very satisfactory reagents for the gravimetric estimation of cobalt in the trivalent state. Dinitroso resorcinol and orcinol form bivalent complexes.

During recent years many organic reagents acting specifically with particular metallic elements have been discovered and extensively investigated. Some of these furnish very accurate reagents for the quantitative estimation of the metals concerned. Thus all aromatic isonitroso-ketones containing the group

α -naphthol, form red insoluble inner complex salts with cobalt, the precipi-

tation being quantitative. But one grave defect of these reagents is that, the precipitate being an arbitrary mixture of divalent complex (II) and trivalent complex (III) is not of pure and definite composition and therefore

not directly weighable. This defect has been indirectly eliminated by Mayer and Feigl (*Ber.*, 1932, 90, 15) who previously oxidised the cobaltous solution to the cobaltic state and then precipitated the metal with α -nitroso- β -naphthol. In the present investigation it has been noted that in these reagents, the number of ketonic oxygen atoms has an important influence on the nature

of the complex formed. When present in this reagent, it helps the precipitation of the 'ous' complex and when absent, that of the 'ic' complex. Thus it has been shown in this paper that α -nitroso- β -naphthylamine

(IV) (Iljenski. *Ber.*, 1884, 17,391) or β -nitroso- α -naphthylamine (Harden, *Annalen*, 1889, 285, 162, 152) which are imino substitution products of the corresponding nitrosonaphthols, produce directly weighable trivalent cobalt complexes (V), no previous oxidation as in the case of Feigl being necessary.

The results of estimation with these reagents are quite accurate. On the other hand, dinitroso-resorcinol (VI) (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 1536) and dinitrosoorcinol (VII) (*Ber.*, 1889, 20, 3133) containing two ketonic

oxygen atoms produce precipitates (VIII and IX) of divalent cobalt.

In the case of *isonitroso dimedone*,

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{Me} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ \text{Me} \end{array} \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_2-\text{CO} \\ \text{CH}_2-\text{CO} \end{array} \right\rangle \text{C}=\text{NOH}$$

(*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 1436), though it contains 2 ketonic oxygen atoms, it produces a directly weighable cobaltic complex

indicating that for the formation of cobaltous complex the presence of benzenoid character, as in the dinitrosoresorcinol, is essential. Here also no previous oxidation is necessary. The precipitates in this case are not so stable as in the other cases.

EXPERIMENTAL.

α-Nitroso-β-naphthylamine (Iljenski, *loc. cit.*; Fischer, *J. pr. Chem.* 1920, 100, 167) was prepared by the action of ammonia on the corresponding nitrosonaphthol, dissolving the product in dilute acid, reprecipitating with ammonia and crystallising from alcohol, when green needles were obtained.

β-Nitroso-α-naphthylamine (Harden, *loc. cit.*) was prepared by heating the corresponding nitrosonaphthol with ammonium chloride and crystallising the product from benzene, when green needles were obtained.

Both the reagents in alcoholic solution produced precipitates with Co, Cu and Ni only. Cobalt precipitation was done as follows.

Procedure.—A nickel-free cobalt chloride solution containing not more than 0.04 g. of cobalt was diluted to 300 c.c. and buffered with sufficient sodium tartrate and acetate and the cobalt was precipitated with 1% alcoholic solution of the reagents. The mixture was boiled for about 20 minutes and allowed to stand for 15 minutes for complete setting and then filtered through a sintered crucible, washed first with dilute acid, then with dilute alkali and then made free from alkali with boiling water, dried at 110° for 1-2 hours and weighed. Exactly the same procedure was adopted in separating cobalt from other elements, but only the *α*-nitroso compound was used, it being very easily obtainable in sufficient quantity in the pure state. The precipitates were stable towards acid, alkali and organic solvents. A sample of the precipitate on analysis gave the following results. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas method and cobalt was estimated as metallic cobalt.

(C₁₀H₇ON₂)₂Co requires : C, 62.93 ; H, 3.67 ; N, 14.68 ; Co, 10.31%

Found *α*-compound : C, 62.8 ; H, 3.67 ; N, 14.51 ; Co, 10.35%

β-compound : C, 62.3 ; H, 3.69 ; N, 14.52 ; Co, 10.38%

TABLE I.

Estimation of cobalt in solution containing or not containing other metal

Co taken.	M/10 Soln. of second metal taken	α -Reagent Co-ppt. obtained.	β -Reagent Co-ppt. obtained.	Calc. wt.	Error (%)
0.01392 g	...	0.1351 g.	...	0.1350 g.	Nil
0.01392	...	0.1354	..	..	+0.3
0.02784	...	0.2703	...	0.2701	Nil
0.03481	...	0.3370	...	0.3377	-0.2
0.01392	...	...	0.1342 g	0.1350	-0.6
0.01392	...	...	0.1351	..	Nil
0.02784	...	...	0.2698	0.2701	-0.1
0.03481	...	...	0.3386	0.3377	+0.3
0.01392	5c.c. ZnSO ₄	0.1350	...	0.1350	Nil
0.01392	5c.c. Alum	0.1354	...	..	+0.3
0.01392	5c.c. Cr ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	0.1354	..	..	+0.3
0.02088	5c.c. MnSO ₄	0.2023	...	0.2025	-0.1

A much larger number of similarly accurate data have been actually collected, but they have not been included in the paper. These two reagents may be freely recommended for accurate estimation of cobalt and for its separation from other elements.

isoNitrosodimedone was prepared by the action of nitrous acid on dimedone and crystallising from aqueous solution by cooling with ice. The aqueous solution produced a precipitate only with cobalt and a slight colouration with nickel and copper. It produced a deep blue colour with iron. The cobalt precipitate was soluble in organic solvents and less stable towards acid than the naphthylamine precipitates. Its molecular weight was also found by the freezing point method to be 572,584.575 against 563, which is the calculated value for a cobaltic complex.

Procedure.—Cobalt solutions containing 0.01 to 0.1 g. or any greater amount was diluted to 200-300 c.c. and heated to 50° and cobalt precipitated with 1-2% aqueous solution of the reagent in slight excess. The temperature was then raised to 70-80° and kept at that range for 10 minutes and then the mixture was allowed to settle. This happened in about one minute. The precipitate was filtered through a sintered crucible washed with

hot water, dried at 100° for 30-45 minutes and weighed. A sample on analysis gave the following results :—

$(C_8H_{10}O_2N)_2Co$ requires : C, 51·1 ; H, 5·32 ; N, 7·44 ; Co, 10·47%
 Found : C, 51·8 ; H, 5·39 ; N, 7·65 ; Co, 10·32%

TABLE II.

Co taken.	Second metal taken.	Ppt. obtained.	Calculated.	Error. (%)
0·03023 g	...	0·2883 g	0·2883 g.	Nil
0·03023	...	0·2887	„	+0·15%
0·06046	...	0·5764	0·5766	Nil
0·09069	...	0·8649	0·8649	Nil
0·03023	0·02896 g. Ni	0·2883	0·2883	Nil
0·01511	„	0·1446	0·1441	+0·3
0·03023	0·01647 g. Cu	0·2884	0·2883	Nil
0·01511	0·00295 g. Cu	0·1446	0·1441	+0·3
0·03023	5c.c.M/10ZnSO ₄	0·2880	0·2883	-0·1
0·03023	„ „ „ MnSO ₄	0·2880	0·2883	-0·1
0·03023	„ „ „ Alum	0·2884	„	Nil
0·03023	„ „ Cr ₃ (SO ₄) ₃	0·2884	„	Nil

A large number of similarly satisfactory data have been omitted. Under proper care, this is the best reagent for quickest and exact estimation of cobalt and its separation from any mixture of metallic salts.

*Dinitrosoresorcinol and Dinitroso orcinol.**

These were prepared by the action of nitrous acid on the phenols. The resorcinol compound was crystallised from a saturated alcoholic solution by cooling. The orcinol compound could not be obtained in the crystalline state. They formed deep reddish brown precipitates with cobalt which are stable towards dilute acids.

Procedure :—(a) *With dinitrosoresorcinol*.—1 G. of reagent was dissolved in 100 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and diluted to 500 c.c. Cobalt

- * (a) Orndorff & Nichols, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923 **45**, 1536
 (b) Beilstein, II, 923, 568 and Kostanecki, *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 31, 33
 (c) Beilstein, VI, 883 (1923)
 (d) Kostanecki, *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 31, 33

solution containing 0.01-0.04 g. cobalt was diluted and heated to boiling and cobalt precipitated with requisite amount of the reagent and digested for 20 minutes and then after cooling was filtered through a sintered crucible under small suction, washed with 15% acetic acid and dried at 115° for 2-3 hours and weighed.

(b) *Dinitroso-orsinol*.—A 0.2% aqueous solution of the reagent was used. Precipitation was done as in the previous case and the precipitate which remained colloidal was coagulated with acetic acid and filtered and dried as previously. Results of estimations are not so accurate, both the complexes retaining a part of the reagents with great tenacity. Samples of the complexes gave the following results on analysis :—

Resorcinol complex requires : C, 36.63 ; H, 1.52 ; N, 14.3 ; Co, 15.01%
($C_6H_4O_4N_2$)₂ Co

Found : C, 37.00 ; H, 1.55 ; N, 13.9 ; Co, 15.2 %

Orcinol complex requires : C, 39.91 ; H, 2.37 ; N, 13.3 ; Co, 14.01%
($C_7H_8O_4N_2$)₂ Co

Found : C, 39.0 ; H, 2.33 ; N, 13.51 ; Co, 13.87%

TABLE III.

Co taken.	Ppt. obtained from resorcinol reagent.	Calc.	Error.
0.02945 g.	0.1960 g.	0.1964 g.	-0.2%
0.02945	0.1950	0.1964	-0.8
0.01472	0.0970	0.0982	-0.12
0.01472	0.0991	0.0982	+1
0.01472	0.1005	0.0982	+2.5
	From orcinol reagent.		
0.02945	0.2100	0.2104	-0.2
0.02945	0.2121	0.2104	+2
0.02945	0.2116	0.2104	+2
0.01472	0.1042	0.1052	-1

These two reagents cannot be freely recommended for accurate estimation of cobalt or for its separation from other elements. The precipitates require a troublesome washing, as the reagents are very easily adsorbed by the precipitates.